

GaN Nanowires for Optoelectronic Devices*

Kris A. Bertness, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Boulder, CO

Single-crystal GaN nanowires have a number of unique properties that make them attractive for future optoelectronic device manufacturing. The nanowires have been shown to have low defect density, high optical output and controllable n-type conductivity.^{1,2} As with most group III nitride semiconductors, p-type doping is possible but challenging. New growth and device processing methods are under development in a number of laboratories around the world, resulting in prototype devices including transistors, light emitting diodes (LEDs), and lasers.³⁻⁶

This talk will focus on nanowires that are grown by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) without a catalyst, resulting in high crystalline purity, very low strain and very low dislocation density. Earlier work⁷ has shown that with this growth method, the dislocations that form to relieve strain move rapidly toward the sidewalls. The dislocations therefore terminate within 5 nm of the nucleation point, and the wire propagates without defects and without strain. The nanowires grow along the c-axis (0001) with m-plane sidewalls {1 -100}, resulting in hexagonal cross-section with diameters most commonly from 100 to 200 nm. Wire diameters vary substantially on neighboring sites, but the lengths are generally uniform to within 5 - 10% in a local area. The length is determined by growth time, although wire coalescence is an issue for longer runs. We have substantial evidence that the wires propagate due to the higher thermodynamic stability of the m-planes relative to the wire end, resulting in low sticking coefficients on the sidewalls and preferential growth at the ends.

The optical properties of the MBE-grown nanowires (see Fig. 1) are similar to those of high quality HVPE GaN. Dominant peaks in low temperature photoluminescence (PL) are donor-bound excitons and free excitons, and the exciton character of the recombination persists up to room temperature. We can readily detect the PL signal from a single nanowire using HeCd laser excitation. Although comparisons with bulk and thick epitaxial GaN are complicated by the higher excitation power density needed to achieve reasonable signal-to-noise from a nanowire, blue and yellow luminescence are absent or weak in nanowire spectra. We also observe PL lifetimes that are similar to those for the best GaN specimens grown with other methods. We have recently demonstrated optically pumped lasing action from a single nanowire with a diameter around 150 nm and a length of 15 μm . Smaller nanowires cannot readily sustain a resonant cavity mode or overcome end facet loss.

In parallel with this work, we have been exploring methods for contacting and manipulating nanowires with the goal of achieving an electrically pumped GaN nanowire laser. Nanowires can readily be dispersed into solvents such as isopropanol and transferred to substrates with pipettes. Contact and bulk resistivity of the wires can be measured by dispersing them onto oxidized silicon followed by ohmic contact deposition using conventional photolithography, for example. Si doping has been varied from below 3×10^{16} to about $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Nanowires can also be placed with dielectrophoresis, in which an electric field directs their motion in a fluid. This process allows us to suspend nanowires across gaps between metal pads to create bridge structures.

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Fig. 1 Low temperature PL spectrum of GaN nanowire. (From Ref. 1)

From an application standpoint, one of the more exciting nanowire characteristics is that this form of GaN combines high quality with low-cost Si substrates. Heterostructures such as radial p-n junctions and axial variations in composition or doping allow many of the same functionality to be grown into nanowires as exists for III-V planar epitaxial structures, although new methods of characterization and growth must be used. The talk will include the latest results on heterostructure formation.

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